

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF LPG ON THE PERFORMANCE AND FRICTIONAL POWER LOSS FOR MULTI CYLINDER SI ENGINE

Pundlik N. Patil

Research Scholar,

Shri Gulabrao Deokar College of Engineering,
Jalgaon (M S), India

pnpatil09@rediffmail.com

Dr.Dheeraj S. Deshmukh

Associate Professor, GH Rasoni College of Engineering,
Nagpur (M S), India

dheerajdeshmukh@raisoni.net

Dr.Vilas. S. Patil

Professor, U I CT KBC North Maharashtra University,
Jalgaon (M S), India

vilaspatil24@yahoo.com

Dr.Manish.S. Deshmukh

Associate Professor, AISSMS College of Engineering,
1-Kennedy Road, Pune (M S), India

msdngp13@gmail.com

Publication History

Manuscript Reference No: IJIRAE/RS/Vol.07/Issue09/SPAE10089

Received: 14, September 2020

Accepted: 26, September 2020

Published Online: 04, October 2020

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26562/ijirae.2020.v0709.003>

Citation: Pundlik,Dr.Dheeraj,Dr.Vilas,Dr.Manish.S (2020). Investigation of the Effect of LPG on the performance and frictional Power Loss for Multi Cylinder SI Engine. IJIRAE::International Journal of Innovative Research in Advanced Engineering, Volume VII, 354-360. <https://doi.org/10.26562/ijirae.2020.v0709.003>

Peer-review: Double-blind Peer-reviewed

Editor-Chief: Dr.A.Arul Lawrence Selvakumar, Chief Editor, IJIRAE, AM Publications, India

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Abstract: The investigation of the effect of engine fuels constitute an important issue in an internal combustion engine research due to deterioration and the sharp rise of conventional fossil fuels those creating the effect on a performance of engine, economy as well as the environmental pollution created by conventional fossil fuels. As the major contributor for fuel consumptions are automotive sector and in this the internal combustion engine plays a major role as power source prime movers. In this present study, the investigation of the effect of LPG fuel on performance of spark ignition engine with frictional power losses in a four stroke four cylinder petrol engine with bifuel mode of operation are carried out with both the fuel with required modification on four stroke four cylinder spark ignition engine at various load and variable speed condition and brake power, indicated power and frictional power are found out along with the various performance parameters. From this analysis, it is found that the brake power decreases for LPG fuel than that of gasoline fuel approximately 6% –9% and the frictional power losses are on higher side, volumetric efficiency and mechanical efficiency are lower down for LPG fuel.

Keywords: Liquefied Petroleum Gas, Indicated Power, Frictional Power Loss, Viscosity, Mechanical Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

Internal combustion engines are seen every day in automobiles, trucks, and buses. The name internal combustion refers also to gas turbines except that the name is usually applied to reciprocating internal combustion engines like the ones found in everyday automobiles. The purpose of internal combustion engine is to produce the mechanical power from chemical energy contained in the fuel. During this conversion, further loss as frictional loss reduced the brake power for the engine, so this energy should be converted with minimum frictional losses. It is well known that reduction of engine mechanical friction always enhance the performance, increases the engine life and efficiency .It is the fact that large percentage of mechanical friction loss in engine is generated on the lubricated surfaces between the piston cylinder assemblies as a rubbing friction.

By considering energy consumption within the engine, it is found that the frictional loss is the major contributor in engine cylinder, nearly two-third of energy is caused by piston skirt friction, piston ring, and bearing while about one-third of energy is due to valve train, crankshaft, transmission and gears. Brake power output of LPG in petrol engine is reduced by about 10 percent as compared to petrol fuel [3,4]. For it, engine performance can be verified by using Morse test which is suitable for high speed multi cylinder engines to find the frictional power and indicated power. In this study the Morse test [1] is conducted on test engine with bi-fuel mode with petrol and Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) as fuel.

The Gaseous fuels such as LPG have been extensively used in commercial modern internal combustion economy engines due to better and lower emissions which makes the attractive fuel at present and they can be categorized as the conventional and alternative fuels. The conventional fuels have been used since the beginning of automotive transports and in other applications. Now days, the engine design has been adjusted to assure the better and effective combustion of the conventional fuels for good performance, better economy and less emissions. Spark ignition engines are designed to run on the petrol as opposed to compression ignition engine which are fueled by diesel and alternative fuels are those that can be used as petrol or diesel oil replacement. In Spark ignition engine, petrol is a mixture of hydrocarbon with the boiling point ranging from 30-215°C and contains aromatic naphthane and paraffin hydrocarbon with their derivatives, because it is necessary to obtain the fuel i.e highly resistant to combustion knock, It is advantageous to have a high content of isoparaffin and aromatic hydrocarbons produced in the reforming processes, gas is considered due to its certain advantages at low constant favorable pollutant emission, high resistance to combustion knock, easy air fuel mixing, high ignition energy with higher octane rating, but at the same time this fuel are having some drawbacks such as mechanical and volumetric efficiencies are lower causing the power loss[5] as well as they increase while LPG is commonly used as a fuel in spark ignition engine which is a mixture of two hydrocarbons mainly as propane and butane.

Table 1. LPG and Petrol Properties[7]

Characteristics	Petrol	LPG
Chemical Formula	C ₈ H ₁₈	C ₃ H ₈ -30% C ₄ H ₁₀ -70%
Lower Heating Value	43957	46500
Density (Kg/m ³)	0.750	0.530
Stoichometric Air fuel ratio	14.6	15.7
Auto ignition temp. (°C)	371	450
Upper flammability limit in air, Kg of Air/Kg of fuel	7.6	5.0
Lower Flammability Limit in air, Kg of Air/Kg of fuel	1.3	9.6
Flame Speed cm/s	37.5	37.0

Some notable findings with LPG as fuels are also found out under the study are as following [6].

- The dominant use of LPG as a automobile fuel at the present state of technology is very difficult to control dispensing into the suction manifold in gaseous state and to minimize it, liquefied petroleum gas is to be evaporated by heating with cooling liquid which requires starting of cold engine in gasoline.
- The evaporated liquefied petroleum gas cannot cool or clean the injector which also gives leads to periodical dosing of gasoline to the engine fuel with LPG.
- LPG dispensing makes the use of additives more difficult, additives that could remove advantages compare to gasoline.

The use of alternative fuel as liquefied petroleum gas, the frictional power losses in internal combustion engine are always affected the performance of engine. So the performance analysis of study is taken in consideration for further research analysis.

II. TEST FACILITY FOR EXPERIMENTATION

The Experimental set up consist of a four stroke four cylinder, carbureted water cooled spark ignition engine naturally aspirated Premier Fiat 1.1litre capacity with maximum output 39 BHP@4800 rpm coupled to hydraulic dynamometer. This spark ignition engine is converted into bi-fuel mode for petrol and LPG fuel by installing bi-fuel conversion with LPG kit. The converted engine will have flexibility of operating either on conventional petrol or LPG. The engine is fitted on a rigid bed and is coupled through a flexible coupling to hydraulic dynamometer which act as a loading device. The cooling water pipe line is connected to a water supply line. Fuel consumption is measured by a calibrated burette for 50 ml quantity of petrol and LPG fuel consumption is measured by electronic weight balance. The air consumption measured by using a mild steel tank which is fitted with a standard orifice and U-tube manometer that measure the pressure inside the tank for the height of the air column. To conduct a Morse test, an arrangement is provided to cut off the ignition to each spark plug. A digital temperature indicator is used to read the temperature of the exhaust gas and cooling water inlet and outlet thermocouple.

The thermocouples are fitted on well-provided in the pipelines. The exhaust gas pipe is connected to a shell tube type heat exchanger wherein the gases are cooled by a cooling water line.

Fig. 1: Experimental Set-up

Separate thermo couples are provided to measure the exhaust gas outlet temperature from calorimeter and calorimeter cooling water inlet and outlet temperature. A charged battery is used to start the engine and the rotameter is used for the measurement of water flow to the engine. The test is carried out to find the power developed in each cylinder for the engine and it basically gives the relationship between brake power and indicated power. It is assumed that friction and pumping losses do not change and remain same when the cylinder is in firing condition as well as in inoperative condition. Using this test ,the frictional losses in the SI engine can be easily calculated. The main intention of carrying out this morse test in SI engine is to provide an easy method of calculating the frictional losses. The total brake power of the engine is first calculated using a dynamometer and the process is repeated with one cylinder off at each step and the difference between total brake power and brake power of remaining cylinder gives the indicated power of first cylinder and so on. Once friction power is obtained the mechanical efficiency of the engine can be calculated [20].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Miqdam T Chaichan, Jaafer Ali Kudham, Khalid Sadiqe Riza 2016[19]: They investigated that the gasoline bp was higher than NG and LPG compression ratio 8:1. The bp for the three fuels was converged when the engine was run a HUCR (higher useful compression ratio) for each fuel Also NG engine's BSFC was less than that of LPG which in turn was less than that caused by gasoline fuel.

Norrizal Mustafa, Mas Fawzi, Fatahul Hakim Zulkifi, Shahrul Osman 2016[3]: They discussed the effect of LPG on volumetric efficiency that the power output and volumetric efficiency of gasoline is higher compared to LPG because gasoline is injected in a liquid form and as it vaporizes, it cools the air and thus produce improved volumetric efficiency. The vaporizer or liquid LPG fuel injection leads to discharging intake air because gaseous nature will occupy the space and reduce the amount of air entering in the engine cylinder. Most of LPG conversion inject the fuel at intake system or intake manifold and the vaporization of fuel depends on the factor such as pipes, thermal insulation, ambient air and liquid fuel temperature, shape and dimension of the intake system, heat of vaporization of the fuel, load and the rotational speed of the engine. Even though, the power output of LPG fuel is lower than gasoline fuel due to its volumetric efficiency, the uses of LPG as a fuel for spark ignition engine still increasing in many countries due to its lower emission and economically.

Gumus, 2012 [12] Found out the effect of variation in volumetric efficiency and engine performance at different mixture of LPG usage as 25% , 50% , 75% and 100% on an engine which is equipped with electronically controlled multipoint sequential gas injection system. The experiments were carried out at constant engine speed (3800 rpm) and with varying loads .The author found that the volumetric efficiency decreased considerably with the use of 25% LPG. As for the 50%, 75% and 100% LPG usage, volumetric efficiency decreased in proportion to LPG usage level while the engine performance gives a positive result only at 25% LPG mixture ratio. Positive results were obtained at all LPG usage levels in terms of exhaust emissions. Best results were obtained at using 100% LPG for exhaust emissions.

Baris Erkus, Ali Surmen and M. Ihsan Karamangil, 2013 [13] investigated the effect of electronically controlled gas phase manifold LPG injection system on the SI engine performance fueled with LPG. Experimentation were carried out at 2000-4000 rpm and fixed throttle position of 25% and 45% of full opening.

During the tests, the excess air coefficient was maintained in the range of 0.95 to 1.05. The results obtained from LPG injection were compared with results obtained from gasoline and LPG carburetion.

Mr. Sanjay D Bisen and Mr. Yogesh R. Suple, 2013 [14] presents the effect of direction injection (DI) of LPG in the chamber of single cylinder four stroke engine with the help of a nozzle. Experiments were carried out at 400 rpm and at variable loads and the final result obtained showed the decrease in bsfc with increase in brake power for LPG as compared to gasoline. When using the LPG as a fuel, the brake thermal efficiency values slightly higher than gasoline and the value of volumetric efficiency for LPG was lower than that of gasoline.

Thirumal mamidi and Dr. J.G. Suryawnsi, 2012 [15] carried out the experimental investigation to evaluate the performance of a single cylinder four stroke SI engine fueled with LPG at variable loads and at various compression ratios, the result obtained showed an increase in mass of fuel consumption for LPG at both the compression ratios when compared to gasoline. It was evaluated that Brake specific energy consumption (BSEC) for LPG values slightly higher than gasoline due to high calorific value but the brake thermal efficiency values slightly higher for gasoline than LPG at both the compression ratios.

Shankar K. S, Mohanan P, 2011 [16] investigated the effect of variation in ignition timing on the performance of a four cylinder multipoint port fuel injection retrofitted gasoline engine to run with LPG injection. Experiments were conducted at varying engine speed at 5° BTDC and then advancing the timing to 6° BTDC and thereafter retarding the ignition timing to 4° and 3° BTDC. It was observed that at 5° BTDC the brake thermal efficiency of LPG is less than gasoline at lower engine speeds but at higher engine speed after 3500 rpm LPG exhibits higher thermal efficiency than gasoline. Since the ignition temperature is high for LPG therefore combustion duration is more and this decreases average burning rate. To accommodate this effect, engine consumes more fuel and thus decreases in efficiency observed. But at higher engine speeds, the flame propagation speed of LPG is increased which lowers the time duration for each cycle and thus demands more rate of combustion and hence efficiency increases.

Ali M. Pourkhesalian, Amir H. Shamekhi and Farhad Salimi, 2009 [4] investigated the performance of a four stroke, four cylinder SI engine fueled with different alternative fuels. They are evaluated that the engine fueled with gaseous fuels resulted in decrease in volumetric efficiency and power output, as gaseous fuels have low density as compared to gasoline. Power and torque mainly depend on an engine's in-cylinder mixture mass. Therefore volumetric efficiency plays one of the most important roles among the other engine parameters. BSFC for gaseous fuels was found to be lowered because they have high heating value as compared to gasoline. Volumetric efficiency reaches to its maximum peak and then decreases because of high pressure loss and choking in high engine speeds. As liquid fuels have latent heat of vaporization, they produce a cooling effect on intake charge during vaporization.

Hakan Bayratkar and Orhan Durgun, 2005 [17] were developed a quasi dimensional model to predict the performance of SI engine fueled with LPG, in this model the combustion chamber is divided into two zones, zone one contains unburned mixture and zone two contains burned mixture. This model solves basic governing differential equation for all the four strokes. Results obtained from the model were compared with the experimental data and was concluded that the LPG reduces the volumetric efficiency and hence the power output and LPG had an adverse effect on engine structural elements because of increase in temperature and pressure due to decrease in combustion duration as burning rate of LPG is high. On the other hand reduction in the mole fractions of CO were found to be 4-5.3% while that of NO was found to be 1-50% for varied engine speeds.

Jehad A. A., H. N. Gupta and B. B. Bansal 2003 [18] developed a computer model for a four-stroke SI engine fuel with LPG in order to predict the effect of combustion duration and engine performance of each other using propane as a fuel and their study confirmed certain combustion duration had to maintained to achieve best engine performance. They also suggested that, the control of emission can be achieved by operating the engine at leaner mixture and their effect on the other variable like Brake Mean Effective Pressure (BMEP) and Basic Specific Fuel Consumption (BSF).

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2: I T EV/s Load

Fig 3: B T E V/s Load

The brake thermal efficiency and Indicated thermal efficiency are always higher for petrol fuel than LPG fuel, since the fuel consumption for LPG is higher than that of petrol and therefore both efficiencies are less for LPG fuel as shown in figure 2 and 3

Fig 4 Fuel consumption V/s Load

Fig. 5 :Sp. fuel consumption V/s Load

In the above figure 4 and 5 shows that the fuel consumption and specific fuel consumption are always less for petrol while it is more in case of LPG as a load and speed and load increases. In experimental Morse test, it is observed that the frictional power losses become more due to increase in indicated power due to more fuel consumption with LPG and due to this the mechanical efficiency is also less for LPG fuels these losses are 10-12% less for petrol fuel as shown in figure 6

Fig. 6 Frictional power V/s Load

Fig. 7 : Volumetric Efficiency V/s Speed

As power and torque mainly depends on engine in cylinder mixture mass and therefore volumetric efficiency plays one of the important role among the other engine parameters. The volumetric efficiency is higher for petrol than LPG fuel as it is in gaseous nature, since petrol is injected in the liquid form and as it vaporizes, it cools the air and produces improved lean mixture of air fuel which leads to improved volumetric efficiency, while the vaporized LPG tends to displace air intake due to its gaseous nature will occupy more volume and reduce the amount of air entering in the engine cylinder and thus volumetric efficiency becomes low as well as brake power will also be reduced as shown in fig. 7

Fig. 8 Mechanical Efficiency V/s Load

The required indicated power is more for LPG fuel and the mechanical efficiency is always lower for LPG due to a sudden rise in BMEP in the cylinder, the heat losses and frictional losses are more as compared to petrol as shown in fig. 8

V. CONCLUSION

From the above experimental investigation, we would conclude the following -

- Due to lower volumetric efficiency, the brake power is also reduced and thereby the Mechanical efficiency are at lower side of LPG fuel by 5-7 %
- Due to more fuel consumption, indicated and brake thermal efficiencies are also affected by LPG fuel, as both efficiencies become less for LPG and the frictional power losses are increased.
- Initially fuel consumption for petrol fuel slightly more but as a load and speed increases, the fuel consumption and specific fuel consumption, both are higher with LPG fuel.
- Among all the above drawback, LPG fuel is also having some advantageous as better antiknock characteristics, high octane rating and cost effective and less emission pollutant for carbon and sulphur.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors are thankful to the SSBT's COET, Jalgaon for providing their kind permission to access the laboratory and library facility. The author would like to thank the staff and colleagues for useful discussions and findings.

REFERENCES

1. J. B. Heywood "Internal Combustion Engine Fundamentals", Tata McGraw Hill, pp 725- 741. (2011)
2. V. Ganeshan , "Internal Combustion Engine", Tata McGraw Hill (2006)
3. Norrizal Mustafa, Mas Fawzi, Fatahu Hakim zulkifi, Shahrul Osman "Effect of volumetric efficiency on spark ignition engine fueled by LPG: A Review." ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences". ISSN 1819-6608,Vol.11. September 2016
4. Ali M. Pourkhesalian, Amir H. Shamekhi, Farhad Salimi, "Performance and Emission Comparison and Investigation of Alternative Fuels in SI Engines," SAE INTERNATIONAL, ISSN: 0148-719.1, 2009.
5. Emilliano Pipitone, Gluseppe Genchi,(Dec. 2014) "Experimental Determination of LPG-gasoline Mixtures Knock Resistance", ASME Journal of Engineering for a Gas Turbine and power, Vol. 136, Issue 12.
6. Maciej Paczuski, Marcin Marchwinay, et all (2016) " Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) as a fuel for Internal Combustion Engines" INTECHS open science pp-123-127
7. C. S. Mistry, (2005) "Comparative assessment on performance of multi-cylinder engine using CNG,LPG and Petrol as a fuel"SAE Technical Paper , 2005-01-1056
8. R. R. Saraf, S. S. Thipse and P. K. Saxsena "Comparative Emission Analysis of Gasolene/LPG (2009). Automotive Bi-fuel Engine.", Word academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 3, No. 3
9. Pundlik Nivrutti Patil, Dr. Dheeraj Sheshrao Deshmukh, "Effect of Liquefied Petroleum Gas as a Fuel on Spark Ignition Engine Performance: A Critical Review" PRATIBHA: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, SPIRITUALITY, BUSINESS AND TECHNOLOGY (IJSSBT), Vol. 4, No. 1, Nov. 2015 ISSN 2277-7261 pp. 50-55
10. Pundlik Nivrutti Patil, Dr. Dheeraj Sheshrao Deshmukh, Jitendra Gulabrao Patil, "A Review on Liquid Petroleum Gas as a Fuel in Spark Ignition Engine Application" International Conference on Global Trends in Engineering, Technology and Management (IJETT), 2016, ISSN: 2231-5381 pp 124-128.
11. Dhiraj S. Deshmukh, Pundlik N. Patil, Vilas, S. Patil(2017) "Design of Experimental plan for Effect of Liquefied Petroleum gas analysis on friction power loss in spark ignition engine", International Conference on Global Trends in Engineering, Technology and Management ISSN: 2320-2882 pp 199- 205.
12. M. Gumus (May 2011) "Effects of volumetric efficiency on the performance and emissions characteristics of a dual fueled (gasoline and LPG spark ignition engine," Fuel Processing Technology, vol.92, pp. 1862-1867
13. Baris Erkus, Ali Surmen, M. Ihsan Karamangil(2013) "A comparative study of carburation and injection fuel supply methods in an LPG-fuelled SI engine," Fuel, vol. 107, p. 511-517,2013
14. Mr. Sanjay D Bisen, Mr. Yogesh R. Suple (10 october 2013) "Performance evaluation of four stroke SI engine by direct injection of LPG," vol. 1, no. 2, ISSN: 2321-8134.
15. Thirumal mamidi, Dr. J.G. Suryawnshi (2012) "Investigations on S.I. Engine Using Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) as an Alternative Fuel," vol. 2, no. 1 ISSN: 2248-9622, pp. 362-367.
16. Shankar K. S, Mohanan P(2011) "MPFI gasoline engine combustion, performance and emission characteristics with LPG injection," Energy and Environment, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 761-770.
17. Hakan Bayraktar, Orhan Durgun (2005) "Investigating the effect of LPG on spark ignition engine combustion and performance," Energy Conversion and management Vol. 46, pp 2317-2333.
18. Jihad A.A., Yamin H. N. Gupta and B. B. Bansal : "The Effect of Combustion Duration on the Performance And Emission Characteristics of Propane-Fueled4-Stroke S1 Engines; Emirates Journal For Engineering Research, 8(1), 1-14 (2003).
19. Miqdam T. Chaichan, Jaafar Ali Kadhum, Khalid Sadiq Riza," Spark Ignition Engine Performance When Fueled with NG, LPG and Gasoline," sjeat," ISSN 2415- 6272 pp. 105-116. Sept. 2016.
20. E. Abu Nada, I. AL Hinti, A. Al Sarkhi, B. Akash, (March 2000) "Effect of Piston Friction on the Performance of SI Engine : A new thermodynamic approach", Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and power, ASME.
21. Tushar Hire, Dr. V.N.Bertaria. (May2014) "Experimental Analysis of piston ring to reduce friction by using different lubricants(SAE15W and SAE30W) for four stroke four cylinder petrol", IJARSE, Vol. 3, Issue 5.